

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Response of different rice varieties to *Azospirillum* sp. inoculation

G. Gopalaswamy and P. Vidhyasekaran,
Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TRRI),
Aduthurai 612101, India

We raised TKM9, ADT36, IR50, and ADT37 during Jul-Oct 1987. Soil was

fertilized with 75 kg N/ha in the form of urea in 3 splits (50%, 25%, 25%), 37.5 kg P/ha in the form of superphosphate (all basal), and 37.5 kg K/ha in the form of muriate of potash (all basal).

Bacterial inoculation was done by soaking 60 kg seeds for 24 h in 60 liters water containing 2 kg peat-based inoculum. Sprouted seeds were sown in the nursery. At 25 d after seeding,

seedlings were pulled up and the roots dipped for 20 min in 40 liters water containing 2 kg inoculum. Another 2 kg inoculum was mixed with 15 kg sand and broadcast in the main field before transplanting. Plot size was 15 m² with 3 replications.

Azospirillum sp. inoculation increased number of productive tillers and straw and grain yield of all test varieties (see table). □

Response of rice varieties to *Azospirillum* inoculation. TRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1987.

Variety	Productive tillers (no./hill)			Straw yield (t/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Without <i>Azospirillum</i>	With <i>Azospirillum</i>	Increase (%)	Without <i>Azospirillum</i>	With <i>Azospirillum</i>	Increase (%)	Without <i>Azospirillum</i>	With <i>Azospirillum</i>	Increase (%)
TKM9	7.1 ± 0.3	8.1 ± 0.7	14	5.4 ± 1.0	6.9 ± 1.3	27	4.4 ± 0.7	5.4 ± 0.9	22
ADT36	6.0 ± 0.4	7.1 ± 0.7	18	4.7 ± 0.2	5.9 ± 0.5	26	4.0 ± 0.1	5.0 ± 0.2	26
IR50	7.2 ± 0.3	8.4 ± 0.3	17	4.2 ± 0.3	5.7 ± 0.7	35	3.6 ± 0.5	5.0 ± 0.4	38
ADT37	5.3 ± 0.5	6.6 ± 0.6	24	4.6 ± 0.3	5.8 ± 0.2	27	3.9 ± 0.2	4.8 ± 0.2	24

Green manure crop performance in semiarid region of India

S. K. Sharma and K. K. Murthy, Agronomy Department, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, Andhra Pradesh, India

A field trial during 1986-1987 wet and dry seasons examined the performance of *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, *S. speciosa*, and *Crotalaria juncea* L.

The 1986 wet season crop was sown 13 May at 30- × 10-cm spacing in 8- ×

2-m plots. This experiment was a single unreplicated plot. The 1986-87 dry season crop was broadcast on 12 Dec in 25- × 4-m plots. The 1987 wet season crop was sown on 6 Jun at 30-cm spacing for *Sesbania* species and 20-cm spacing for *C. juncea* in 25- × 5-m plots. The Dec and Jun experiments were laid

out in a randomized block design with three replications. Fertilizer was 20 kg N and 17.6 kg P/ha, incorporated before sowing. One irrigation was given at sowing for germination.

Plant stands were uniform in all plots. Growth was recorded on 10 plants collected at random at 48 d after sowing

Table 1. Plant height and fresh weight of green manure crops sown in May 1986 in Hyderabad, India.

Green manure crop	Plant height (cm)	Fresh weight (g)
<i>S. aculeata</i>	151.5	172.0
<i>S. rostrata</i>	158.0	158.0
<i>S. speciosa</i>	77.6	69.6

Table 2. Plant height and fresh and dry weight of green manure crops grown in dry (Dec) and wet (Jun) seasons. Hyderabad, India, 1986-87.

Green manure	Plant height (cm)			Fresh weight (g)			Dry weight (g)		
	Dry season 1986	Wet season 1987	Mean	Dry season 1986	Wet season 1987	Mean	Dry season 1986	Wet season 1987	Mean
<i>S. aculeata</i>	38.3	148.0	93.2	10.7	57.3	34.0	2.7	14.0	9.4
<i>S. rostrata</i>	25.3	139.0	82.2	9.4	58.0	33.7	2.4	13.7	9.0
<i>C. juncea</i> L.	29.0	84.0	56.5	6.0	24.3	15.2	1.7	6.0	3.8
Mean	30.9	123.7		8.7	46.6		2.3	11.2	
LSD (0.05)									
Season		9.7		5.0			0.8		
Green manure		11.9		6.1			1.0		
Season × green manure		16.8		8.7			1.4		
CV (%)		12.0		17.2			11.8		